

On Colloidal Electrolytes. An Attempt to Account for the Effect of Dilution on their Osmotic Pressure, Conductivity and Counter Ion Activity

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On the basis of certain assumptions the following equations have been deduced to account for the variation, with dilution, of osmotic pressure and conductance of congo red and of hydrogen ion activity and conductance of cetyl sulphonic acid sols

$$P_c = P_m \frac{C}{C+K} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$X_c - X_0 = X_m [1 + \beta(C - C_d)] \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$H_c - H_0 = a_m [1 + \beta(C - C_d)] \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad \dots (3)$$

In equation (1) P_c represents the osmotic pressure at the concentration C , of congo red and P_m and K are constants. P_m represents the osmotic pressure of the counter ions within the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the osmometer membrane. Its biological significance has been discussed.

In equation (2) X represents the specific conductivity at the concentration, C , of the micelle forming electrolyte, C_0 , its c.m.c., C_d , the concentration at which the diffuse double layers overlap, X_0 the specific conductivity corresponding to C_0 and X_m , β , and K , are constants.

In equation (3) H_c represents the hydrogen ion activity at the concentration, C , of cetyl-sulphonic acid, C_0 , the c.m.c. and H_0 , the hydrogen ion activity corresponding to C_0 . The other terms have the same significance as in equation (2).

The equations have been found to agree well with the experimental results on congo red obtained by Donnan and Harris and on cetylsulphonic acid obtained by McBain and Williams. The minimum in equivalent conductivity at about $C = 0.094$ N has been shown to be mainly due to the suppression of ionisation of the molecularly dispersed cetylsulphonic acid at the c.m.c. level which latter is also lowered to some extent.

The colloidal electrolytes, according to their behaviour in solution, have so far been treated^{1,2,3,4,5} on the basis of the classical theories proposed for the weak or strong electrolytes. By following such treatment, however, many of the observed facts cannot be accounted for satisfactorily.

In this paper it will be shown how the aforesaid properties of the micellar or association colloids such as congo red and cetylsulphonic acid can be accounted for fairly quantitatively

on the basis of a new mode of approach proposed by the author⁶ to explain the Pallmann effect.

It is based on the following assumptions :

I. That each micelle or colloidal particle is surrounded by an electrical double layer made up of two parts, (1) the fixed Stern-Mukherjee⁸ layer and (2) the diffuse double layer (i.e. the Gouy-Chapman layer).

II. The counter ions cannot go beyond the boundary of the diffuse double layer of the micelle to which they belong. When a micelle moves sufficiently close to the osmometer membrane or to the reversible electrode placed in the sol, so that the diffuse double layer is in contact with the membrane or the electrode, then only the counter ions present in this portion of the double layer can register their activity on the membrane or the reversible electrode.

III. Starting from the outermost boundary of the diffuse double layer, the activity of the counter ions increases according to the Boltzmann distribution law as the surface of the micelle or particle is approached.

IV. In the case of a micellar or association colloid it is assumed that if C_0 represents the critical micelle concentration then the number of micelles, X , in unit volume, at a stoichiometric concentration, C , of the micelle forming electrolyte is equal to $k_0(C - C_0)$, where k_0 is a proportionality constant and $C \gg C_0$.

I. *The equation for Osmotic Pressure* : Suppose the osmometer consists of two chambers separated by a membrane, one of the chambers containing the micelle forming electrolyte at a concentration, C , much higher than C_0 its c.m.c. and the other containing water. The number of micelles X per unit volume of the sol is equal to $k_0(C - C_0)$ as already stated. The molecularly dispersed electrolyte at the c.m.c. level can pass through the membrane, but the micelles cannot. The counter ions present in the diffuse double layer of a micelle can register their activity on the osmometer membrane only when the micelle carries them sufficiently close to it (membrane) so that the diffuse double layer is in contact with it. If p , be the number of micelles and \bar{A} the average area of the diffuse double layer of each in contact with unit area of the membrane, then the fraction of the surface, per unit area of the membrane covered, is $p\bar{A} = \theta$. Let the activity of the counter ions within the diffuse double layer, associated with a unit area of it, at the plane of contact with the membrane be a_s . Then the activity of the counter ions with which each unit area of the membrane is in contact is, $p\bar{A}a_s = \theta a_s$.

At the point of contact, the diffuse double layer is somewhat distorted and so the activity and consequently the osmotic pressure at this portion of the diffuse double layer is to some extent higher than that in the surrounding liquid and this tends to remove the micelle from the membrane.

If S , be the total surface area of the membrane and θ , the fraction per unit area, covered by the diffuse double layers of the micelles, the concentration of which is x , then the rate at which the micelles (i.e., their double layers) come in contact with the membrane is $k_1 S(1 - \theta)x$ and the rate at which they are removed from the surface is $k_2 S\theta$ where k_1 and k_2 are constants.

Therefore at equilibrium

$$k_1 S(1-\theta)x = k_2 S\theta \quad \dots (1)$$

or

$$\theta = \frac{x}{k_2/k_1+x} = \frac{(C-C_0)}{K+(C-C_0)} \quad \dots (2)$$

where $x = k_0(C-C_0)$ and $K = (k_2)/(k_1 k_0)$

The osmotic pressure of the counter ions should be proportional to θ . If P represents the osmotic pressure of the counter ions at the concentration C of the micelle forming electrolyte then

$$P_c = RTa_s\theta = P_m\theta = P_m \frac{(C-C_0)}{K+(C-C_0)} \quad \dots (3)$$

where $P_m = RTa_s$ and a_s has the same significance as explained already.

It may be pointed out that so long as $C > C_0$, C_0 will not change with dilution, but remain constant and so P_m and a_s will also remain constant.†

It may be mentioned that in the aforesaid deduction the contribution of the micelles to osmotic pressure has been assumed to be negligible. Furthermore, since the c.m.c. is small its effect on osmotic pressure, due to Donnan equilibrium can be neglected.

1(a). *The Osmotic Pressure of Congo Red Sol*: The osmotic pressure of congo red sol (freed from NaCl by dialysis) has been measured by Donnan and Harris⁹. They have found that the observed osmotic pressure, P is somewhat smaller than that calculated from the equation $P = RTC$ where C is the molecular concentration of congo red assumed to be completely undissociated. This led to the conclusion that a fairly large number of anions have associated to form a micelle* which may include as many Na⁺ ions in the undissociated form as there are anions in it. The remaining Na⁺ ions are almost completely dissociated. Writing Co', for the anions it may be represented as Na (CONa)⁻. Since the osmotic pressure has been found to be smaller than that of the ionisable Na⁺ ions, Zsigmondy has suggested that the activity of the Na⁺ ions has been reduced owing to interionic attraction as postulated by the Debye-Huckel theory. Van Rysselberghe⁵ has attempted to account for the low activity of the Na⁺ ions quantitatively on the basis of the Debye-Huckel theory, but his attempts have not met with much success.

Equation (3) has been tested using the data of Donnan and Harris⁹. Since C_0 for congo red is very small compared to C it has been neglected. The equation (3) has, therefore, been used in the form

$$P_c = P_m \frac{C}{K+C} \quad \dots (3a)$$

† The sol of the colloidal electrolyte being pure, the concentration of molecularly dispersed electrolyte in it is C_0 which does not change with dilution. Therefore, the thickness of the diffuse double layer and the distribution of ions within it should not change with dilution. Hence P_m and a_s should remain constant.

* A micelle of congo red is assumed to contain a large number of anions so that at a stoichiometric concentration of 0.1732N (i.e., 0.0866M) the double layers of the micelles do not overlap.

The constants P_m and K have been found to be 1.5×10^4 and 1.74 respectively.

As congo red contains some NaCl it was subjected to dialysis by Donnan and Harris and the maximum pressure observed when free from NaCl was recorded. When the dialysis was continued still further the pressure was found to fall slowly, very probably due to slow aggregation of the micelles. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

C in equivalent of Na^+ per litre	$P_m = 1.5 \times 10^4$ mm of Hg.		$K = 1.74$
	P observed in mm of Hg	P calculated from eqn (3a) in mm of Hg	* P calculated from eqn : $P = RTC_1$
0.1732	1363	1358	1567
0.1440	1139	1147	1304
0.0751	603	621	676
0.0366	310	309.3	331.8
0.0217	185.5	184.8	196
0.0164	140	140.3	148.7
0.0111	97.0	95.3	100.5
0.00738	62.5	63.3	66.7

* $C_1 = C/2$ i.e., molar concentration.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that the values of P calculated from equation (3a) agree satisfactorily with those observed. In column 4 of the table are recorded the values of P calculated by Donnan and Harris⁹ using the equation $P = RTC_1$ where C_1 represents the molecular concentration of congo red assumed to be completely undissociated.* Even then, their calculated values are higher than the observed ones.

Attention may be drawn to the fact that P_m in equation (3) or (3a) represents the osmotic pressure exerted by the counter ions within the diffuse double layer at the plane of contact with the osmometer membrane and it is about 20 atmospheres. This leads to the conclusion that if the counter ions were not confined within the boundaries of the diffuse double layers but were allowed free movement in the intermicellar liquid then the observed pressure would have been much higher.

Its biological significance is worth noting. In an animal cell the protein molecules are negatively charged and if the counter ions in the diffuse double layer of each of them were free to move about within the cell then the osmotic pressure they would have exerted on the cell wall might have been high enough to rupture it, but owing to the restriction imposed on their movement by the double layer the osmotic pressure they can exert is proportional to θ only.

* In calculating osmotic pressure Donnan and Harris used Na_2CO as the molecular formula of congo red.

2(a). *The equation of specific conductivity* : Concentration of micelles not high enough for the diffuse double layer to overlap.

Since the absolute velocity of the ions (except H^+ and OH^- ions) lies between 3×10^{-4} and 7×10^{-4} cm. and the time, during which the current passes in a given direction is 10^{-3} seconds (1000 cycle), therefore, the distance an ion can travel in a particular direction in conductivity measurements should lie between 3×10^{-7} and 7×10^{-7} cm. Furthermore, under the retarding influence of the electrical double layer of a colloidal particle, the distance a counter ion can travel, should be much smaller still. The thickness of the diffuse double layer¹⁰ of a micelle or colloidal particle in contact with a 0.001*N* solution of a uni-univalent electrolyte is about 10^{-6} cm. Therefore, in the measurements of conductivity of a colloidal system the counter ions which can reach an electrode must proceed from the diffuse double layers (of the particles) just in contact with the electrode surface.

Let the number of univalent counter-ions within the diffuse double layer, associated with an unit area of it at the plane of contact with an electrode of the conductivity cell, be n gram ions. Then the contribution to specific conductivity by the micelles* and their counter ions should be equal to :

$$p\bar{A}nF(\bar{U} + \bar{V}) = \theta nF(\bar{U} + \bar{V})$$

where \bar{U} and \bar{V} are the average absolute velocities of a counter ion and a micelle respectively. and the other terms have the same significance as explained already.

The contribution of the molecularly dispersed electrolyte corresponding to the concentration, C_0 at the c.m.c. level should be equal to :

$$(1-\theta)C_0\alpha F(U+V)$$

where α is the degree of dissociation and U and V represent the velocities of the cation and the anion respectively.

Hence the specific conductivity X of the system, consisting of micelles and molecularly dispersed electrolyte at the c.m.c. level, should be found from the expression

$$\begin{aligned} X_c &= \theta nF(\bar{U} + \bar{V}) + (1-\theta)\alpha C_0F(U+V) \\ &= \theta[nF(\bar{U} + \bar{V}) - \alpha C_0F(U+V)] + \alpha C_0F(U+V) \end{aligned} \quad \dots \quad (4b)$$

Putting X_s for $nF(\bar{U} + \bar{V})$ and X_0 for $\alpha C_0F(U+V)$ equation (4b) may be written as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} X_c - X_0 &= (X_s - X_0)\theta = (X_s - X_0)\frac{C - C_0}{K + (C - C_0)} \\ &= X_m \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \end{aligned} \quad \dots \quad (4c)$$

So long as $C > C_0$ dilution does not change C_0 and hence α , X_0 , X_s and X_m remain constant provided the double layers do not overlap. It is to be noted that X_0 is always very small compared to X_s .

* Since the double layer, as a whole, is electrically neutral therefore, corresponding to the electrical charge $\bar{A}nF$ of the counter ions the charge on the micelle, for area \bar{A} at the plane of contact, must be $\bar{A}nF$ and opposite in sign.

2(b). *The micelle-concentration is high enough for the diffuse double layers to overlap* : If it is assumed that about 40 molecules associated to form a micelle and that the c.m.c. is $0.005N$ then at a concentration of $0.1N$ of the micelle forming electrolyte (assumed to be strong and uni-univalent) the distance between the centres of two neighbouring micelles is about 0.87×10^{-6} cm. and at room temperature the thickness of the electrical double layer surrounding each micelle is about 0.44×10^{-6} cm. At 90° the thickness of the double layer should be larger still and hence the diffuse double layers should begin to overlap even below $0.1N$.

The overlapping of the diffuse double layers of the micelles may affect the specific conductivity of the system in three ways :

(i) Before overlapping, the ions of the micelle forming electrolyte at the c.m.c. level are distributed mostly in the intermicellar liquid, beyond the boundaries of the double layers, but when overlapping occurs they are placed within the double layers where the activity of the counter ions is quite high. This tends to lower the c.m.c. of the electrolyte and suppress its dissociation if it is a weak electrolyte or if it is a strong electrolyte, U and V of its ions inside the double layer owing to strong electrostatic attraction will be much smaller than those outside the double layer and consequently its contribution X_0 to specific conductivity will be much reduced.

(ii) Since the overlapping double layers repel each other the electrostatic force of attraction on the counter ions (after overlapping) will be comparatively less than it was before overlapping and hence their mobility should increase. Effects (i) and (ii) should cancel each other to some extent at the initial stage but at a later stage (ii) may preponderate over (i), provided the velocity of the micelles does not decrease much.

(iii) The third effect of overlapping is to increase, n , in equation (4b) proportionately with the extent of overlapping and therefore, proportionately with the *further* increase in micelle concentration.

The net effect will be an increase in the specific conductivity of the system. This may be accounted for by replacing X_m in equation (4c) by $X_m[1 + \beta(C - C_a)]$, where β is a constant and C_a is the concentration near about which overlapping begins. Introducing this change in equation (4c) it may be written as follows,

$$X_e - X_0 = X_m[1 + \beta(C - C_a)] \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad \dots (5)$$

It is to be noted that when $C \leq C_a$ equation (5) is reduced to equation (4c) and for values of $C > C_a$, X_0 is decreased.

2(c). *Specific conductance of Congo red and Cetylsulphonic acid sols* : The specific conductivity of congo red sol (freed from NaCl by dialysis) has been measured by Donnan and Harris⁹. Their data along with those calculated from equation (4c) neglecting C_0 are recorded in Table II.

The specific conductance of cetylsulphonic acid sol has been measured by McBain and Williams¹¹ at 90° . Hartley *et al.*¹² from a consideration of the behaviour of cetylpyridinium

bromide and cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide have concluded that the c.m.c. of cetyl-sulphonic acid should be lower than 0.01*N*. Its equivalent conductivity shows a sharp fall below 0.005 *N_w** or 0.0048 *N_v*. We have, therefore, taken its c.m.c. as 0.005 *N* or 0.0048 *N_v*. The data of McBain and Williams¹¹ along with those calculated from equation (5) are recorded in Table III.

TABLE II

Congo red sol.

$$X_0 = 2.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ recip.ohms.} \quad X_m = 1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ recip.ohms.} \quad K = 0.067$$

Moles/litre	Specific conductivity $\times 10^3$	
	Observed	Calculated from equation (4c)
0.0357	3.66	3.50
0.01785	2.05	2.12
0.00892	1.13	1.19
0.00446	0.626	0.644
0.00223	0.352	0.342
0.001116	0.189	0.184
0.000558	0.102	0.102

TABLE III

Cetylsulphonic acid sol. (conductivity)

$$K = 3.0; \quad T = 90^\circ; \quad X_0 = 0.001467 \text{ recip.ohms}; \quad \beta = 0.6; \quad C_0 = 0.0048 \text{ } N_v;$$

$$X_m = 0.602 \text{ recip.ohms}; \quad C_a = 0.09359 \text{ } N_v$$

<i>N_v</i>	Specific conductivity		Equivalent conductivity	
	Observed	Calculated	Observed	Calculated
0.5429	0.1196	0.1174	220.4	216.2
0.4169	0.08706	0.08728	208.9	209.4
0.2236	0.04504	0.04542	201.5	203.1
0.09359	0.01650	0.01877	176.4	200.5
		(0.01767)		(188.8)
0.04502	0.00950	0.00943	211.0	209.5
0.00963	0.00247	0.00243	256.2	252.9

It appears from Table II that in the first three cases the difference between the observed and the calculated values of specific conductivity of congo red sol lies within $\pm 5\%$. The high observed value in the first case may be attributed to the presence of a small quantity

* *N_w* and *N_v* represent normal solutions by weight and volume respectively.

of NaCl as an impurity while the two low values may be due to slight aggregation of the micelles on dilution so that the values of C used for calculation in equation (4c) are a little higher than the actual values. This inference receives some support from the observation of Donnan and Harris⁹ (as stated already) that when NaCl was removed by dialysis the osmotic pressure rose to a maximum and then began to fall slowly with further dialysis. This subsequent fall in osmotic pressure is very probably due to the aggregation of the micelles to some extent.

It will be noticed from the data recorded in Table III that the agreement between the values of specific conductivity observed and those calculated from equation (5) is satisfactory in all the cases except for $N_v = 0.09359$. In calculating the specific conductivity at this N_v , the contribution X_0 of the molecularly dispersed cetylsulphonic acid at the c.m.c. level ($0.0048 N_v$) has been taken as 0.001467 recip. ohms. For reasons stated already under (i) this value needs correction. McBain and Williams¹¹ consider cetylsulphonic acid to be much weaker than HCl. Assuming that it obeys Ostwald's dilution law and that its degree of ionisation at $0.005 N$ to be 80% its dissociation constant is found to be 1.6×10^{-2} . McBain and Williams¹¹ have found from potentiometric measurements that the degree of ionisation of $0.00723 N$ cetylsulphonic acid is about 79%, so for the $0.005 N_w$ acid 80% may be taken as the approximate value for its degree of ionisation. Again, according to McBain and Williams¹¹, the degree of ionisation of cetylsulphonic acid between $1.0 N_w$ and $0.01 N_w$ is nearly constant and its average value is 63%. It, therefore, follows that the activity of the H^+ ions of $0.1 N_w$ solution of the acid is 0.063. The activity of the H^+ ions within the overlapping double layers cannot, therefore, be less than 0.063. Using this value and the dissociation constant of the acid as, 1.6×10^{-2} , the degree of ionisation of the molecularly dispersed acid within²the overlapping double layers is found to be about 20% only. Since the specific conductivity of the molecularly dispersed acid at the c.m.c. level (i.e., $0.005 N_w$) when it is 80% dissociated is 0.001467 , therefore, its specific conductivity when it is 20% dissociated should be about 0.00037 recip. ohms. Hence if this value (i.e., 0.00037) instead of 0.001467 is used in calculating the specific conductance X_c at $0.09359 N_v$ then it is found to be 0.01767 which is much closer to the observed value, 0.0165 . This corrected specific conductivity and the corresponding corrected equivalent conductivity are recorded in Table III enclosed by brackets.

If the value of $X_0 = 0.00037$ is used in calculating the values of X_c above $0.09359 N_v$, then these values would be lower than those recorded in Table III by 0.0011 . The lowering may be compensated by suitably increasing β , in equation (5) by about 2 or 3%.

3(a). *The equation for the activity of the counter ions*: It follows from the discussion recorded already that if H_c and H_0 be the activities of the counter ions indicated by a reversible electrode at the concentration, C and C_0 (i.e., c.m.c.) respectively of the micelle forming electrolyte, then

$$H_c = a\theta + H_0(1-\theta) \quad \dots (6)$$

or

$$H_c - H_0 = (a_s - H_0)\theta = a_m \frac{x}{k_2/k_1 + x} = a_m \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad \dots (6a)$$

So long as $C > C_0$, H_0 and a_s and, therefore, a_m remain constant.

At a sufficiently high concentration C of the micelle forming electrolyte, when the number of micelles per unit volume of the sol is such that their double layers begin to overlap, equation (6a), for the reasons stated already, should assume the form

$$H_c - H_0 = a_m [1 + \beta(C - C_d)] \frac{(C - C_0)}{K + (C - C_0)} \quad \dots \quad (6b)$$

where β is a constant and the other terms have the same significance as stated already.

3(b). *Hydrogen ion activity of Cetylsulphonic acid sol at various dilutions*: McBain and Williams¹¹ have measured at 90° the H⁺ ion activity of cetylsulphonic acid sols at several concentrations by the potentiometric method. They have also measured the e.m.f. of HCl solutions at different concentrations at 90° and constructed a graph by plotting the e.m.f. against the concentration of HCl. From the graph they have found the concentration of HCl which corresponds to the e.m.f. indicated by a particular concentration of cetylsulphonic acid. Thus the concentration of cetylsulphonic acid and the concentration of HCl, both having the same H⁺ ion activity are found. Taking the activity coefficient of a very dilute solution of HCl such as 0.000873 as unity, the activities of the HCl solutions of the desired concentrations are found and from these, the activities of the cetylsulphonic acid solutions used, are found.

In Table IV are recorded the data along with the values of H⁺ ion activity calculated from equation (6b).

TABLE IV
Cetylsulphonic acid sol.
H⁺ ion activity

$K = 3.0; \quad C_0 = 0.005 N_w; \quad \beta = 0.35; \quad T = 90^\circ; \quad H_0 = 0.0037; \quad C_d = 0.1 N_w$					
$a_m = 1.9; \quad = 0.09359 N_w$					
N_w	Observed	Calculated from eqn. (6b)	N_w	Observed	Calculated from eqn.(6b)
1.0208	0.628	0.639	0.2084	0.136	0.130
0.6640	0.434	0.414	0.1158	0.0775	0.0751
0.4225	0.250	0.262	0.0700	0.0425	0.0439
0.2432	0.149	0.151	0.0369	0.0234	0.0236

In view of the sources of error involved in the potentiometric method of measuring H⁺ ion activity the agreement between the observed and the calculated values may be taken as satisfactory.

It may be mentioned that below 0.1158 N the term involving $\beta(C - C)$ disappears and equation (6b) reduces to equation (6a).

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